

EXPERIMENTAL VERIFICATION OF THE MODEL OF THE PROCESS OF FORMATION OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF FOREIGN STUDENTS BY MEANS OF INTERACTIVE TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the description of experimental work aimed at verifying the formation of communicative competence of foreign students by means of interactive technologies. The article reflects the stages of experimental research, presents educational and methodological support and conditions necessary for the implementation of the proposed technology.

Keywords: communicative competence, disciplines of special training, foreign language, motivational criterion, functional and communicative criterion, functional and informational criterion, pedagogical tasks.

The study of pedagogical processes and phenomena always requires experimental verification of hypothetical assumptions. A reliable way to obtain data is a pedagogical experiment - a kind of experience that has a cognitive, purposefully research, methodical nature, which is carried out under specially specified conditions [7, 720].

The purpose of our experimental work is to test the model of formation of students' communicative competence in the context of intellectual and communicative interaction of subjects of the educational process at the university. The goal we set predetermined the nature of the main tasks to be solved in the course of experimental work:

- to develop directions and determine the stages of work on testing the model of formation of students' communicative competence at the university;
- to identify evaluation criteria and determine the initial level of formation of communicative competence among university students;

The need to achieve the set goals and objectives led to the appropriate organization of experimental work. In our study, we were guided by a step-by-step approach, according to which any pedagogical experiment is carried out in three stages (preparatory, main, final), at each of which an experiment corresponding to the stage (ascertaining, forming, generalizing) is carried out [8, 155].

At the first stage preparatory work be carried out aimed at studying the psychological and pedagogical literature on the research topic, on the methodology and methodology for determining the level of formation of communicative competence, the apparatus for analyzing and processing the data obtained, preparing materials for the experiment, and identifying the initial level of formation of the studied competence of students (ascertaining experiment).

At the second stage a model is being tested for the formation of students' communicative competence at the university is being tested.

At the third stage the results of experimental work will be analyzed, the dynamics of the level of formation

of the communicative competence of university students was determined, generalizing conclusions will be made, and research materials will be published.

Recently, scientists have been increasingly trying to develop appropriate methods for diagnosing competencies. Pedagogical diagnostics – determination of the quality, productivity of the educational process, its components and results, analysis of causal relationships and assessment.

According to certain criteria and indicators of the degree of achievement of the set goals and objectives of education and upbringing, including its assessment and self-assessment [6, 720].

It is advisable to diagnose the level of competence formation using diagnostic tools: questionnaires, questionnaires, tests, each of which (or their combination) allows you to assess any personal quality of a student that affects his competence. In accordance with the studied components of the university student's communicative competence, we have identified the following criteria:

1. Motivational criterion – the indicators are the dominant motives, stability and orientation of motivation.
2. Intellectual criterion – indicators are knowledge of the basics of intellectual and communicative interaction and intellectual skills (analysis, synthesis, comparison, generalization, etc.).
3. Activity criterion – indicators are stable communication skills and abilities.
4. Reflexive criterion – the indicators are the skills of assessment and reflection.

According to the selected criteria, a set of diagnostic techniques was applied at the stage of the ascertaining experiment. The methodology, unlike the method, provides specific instructions for diagnosis, data processing and interpretation of the results. Within the framework of a single method, there can be an almost infinite number of techniques [10, 9].

In order to determine the level of formation of students' communicative competence, a set of techniques was used, shown in Table 2.

Table 2

Methods for diagnosing the level of formation of students' communicative competence at the university

Criteria	Indicators	Assessment methods and techniques
Motivational	Dominant motives (stability, orientation of motivation to the communication process)	A conversation, a questionnaire. Diagnostics of motivational orientations in interpersonal communications (I.D. Ladanov, V.A. Urazaeva). The methodology for diagnosing the motivation of students (A. A. Rean and V.A. Yakunin (modified by N.C. Badmaeva)
Intelligent	Knowledge of the basics of intellectual and communicative interaction; intellectual skills	Methods of measuring social intelligence (J. Guilford, M. O'Sullivan). The test "Fundamentals of intellectual and communicative interaction".
Activity - based	Communication skills and abilities	Interviewing, observation, questioning, testing. Methodology for assessing the level of sociability V.F. Ryakhovsky. Methodology definitions of G.S. Nikiforov's communication skills and abilities.
Reflexive	Assessment and reflection skills	Conversation, interviewing, observation, testing. A.V. Karpov's methodology for assessing the level of reflexivity of trainees.

Also, during the ascertaining experiment, we determined the average of each component of the competence under study and expressed it as a percentage.

The result is clearly shown in Figure 1. [7, 720]

Figure 1. Summary data on the level of formation of CC components by groups (ascertaining experiment)

It should be noted that the assessment of the formation of competencies is a level one. By the level of competence formation, we mean the degree of completeness of mastering all its elements. The level of competence formation is a measurable indicator and a quantitative characteristic of a student's readiness to demonstrate competence.

The motivational criterion. Considering that the motivational component has a significant impact on the dynamics of the development of communicative competence, first of all, we identified the level of formation of the motivational sphere of students and determined the stability and orientation of motivation to the communication process. To determine the level of formation of the motivational component of the communicative competence of university students, we used the diagnosis of motivational orientations in interpersonal communications, developed by I.D. Ladanov and V.A. Urazaeva [4, 18-22].

The intellectual criterion. In the structure of communicative competence, the intellectual component determines the level of knowledge base and intellectual development of the student. Therefore, to study the level of formation of this component, we developed an intellectual criterion and tested students, both to determine the basic knowledge of the basics of intellectual and communicative interaction, and to identify the level of development of social intelligence. Consequently, the leading research method at this stage was testing, which allowed us to assess the level of knowledge and abilities of each student with a certain probability.

The test, consisting of a set of tasks or questions and conducted under standard conditions, allows you to determine the level of proficiency in any type of activity and relatively accurately identify the level and structure of a student's preparedness [6, 720]. The interpretation of the test results is mainly based on the arithmetic

mean and percentage norms. This interpretation of test results is called normative-oriented [5, 239].

Activity criterion. communicative competence speaks for itself and provides meaningful content from the perspective of skills and abilities of communicative activity, behavioral component. This criterion is actualized in the activity aspect of communicative competence, which reflects the processes of finding, selecting, processing information during intellectual and communicative interaction of subjects, as well as its subsequent preservation and transfer; includes modeling, development of information use cases and forecasting their consequences [11].

A reflexive criterion. To determine the level of formation of the reflexive component of students' communicative competence, we examined its main indicators – reflexive abilities. The high level of formation of the reflexive component of communicative competence, which is based on well-formed reflexive abilities, allows the student, a future graduate of the university, to most effectively and adequately carry out reflexive processes, realize their reflexive abilities, which ensures the process of self-development of creative manifestations, promotes a creative approach to professional activity and achieving its maximum effectiveness [4, 18-22].

The experimental work carried out made it possible to draw the following conclusions:

Based on the theoretical provisions of the first chapter of the dissertation research, a criterion-diagnostic toolkit was developed and a set of diagnostic tools was used according to the selected criteria: motivational, intellectual, activity-oriented, reflective. The results of the ascertaining experiment showed an insufficient level of formation of students' communicative competence, which required the introduction of special tools for its further formation.

The formative stage of experimental work proved the effectiveness of the model being introduced into the educational process, proving the effectiveness of the integration of the proposed pedagogical technologies.

According to the developed model, the most significant results were obtained following the implementation of a number of principles. The principle of intellectual creative activity has found its application as a result of the introduction of critical thinking development technology into the educational process. The variety of techniques used in this technology provided huge opportunities for the development of students' intellectual initiative and contributed to the formation of the intellectual component of their communicative competence. The principle of integration was of great importance for the professional orientation of students. As part of the implementation of this principle, the integrative use of knowledge from general professional and special disciplines was emphasized in order to achieve a holistic result – the student's communicative preparation for future professional activity.

Therefore, we can conclude that the change in the level of formation of communicative competence among students - future teachers is not caused by accidental reasons, but is a consequence of the introduction of the model developed by us into the educational process of the university.

Conclusion

During the experimental work, the effectiveness of the developed model was proved. According to the data obtained, the introduction of our model contributed to an increase in the level of formation of the communicative competence of university students – future economists in all groups, however, in the fourth experimental group, as a result of the integration of all the proposed technologies, the level turned out to be significantly higher, which indicated the effectiveness of introducing a model for the formation of students' communicative competence at the university.

Thus, the correctness of the hypothesis was confirmed that the formation of the communicative competence of university students will be more effective if all the technologies proposed by us are integrated in the learning process.

The conducted dissertation research revealed the general didactic significance of the implementation of the results obtained by us, which confirms the effectiveness of the developed model for the formation of students' communicative competence at the university. However, this does not exhaust the study of this problem and it can be continued in the following directions: identifying patterns in the process of forming the communicative competence of university students, improving technologies for preparing students for intellectual and communicative activities, expanding diagnostic tools to determine the levels of formation of communicative competence among university students.

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